

DURABILITY AND DAMAGE TOLERANCE OF FIBEROUS MATERIAL SYSTEMS: BEHAVIOR AND MODELING

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ABSTRACT

Durability and damage tolerance are controlling factors for many important current and projected applications of composite materials, such as the high speed civil transport aircraft. The importance of such behavior contrasts greatly to our level of understanding or ability to predict it. To address this need, we have taken a mechanistic (micromechanical) approach, in which we attempt to characterize and model changes in strength in terms of the parameters which define and control the processes which determine durability and damage. These models are then assembled into a performance simulation code which increments the constituent (and interface / interphase) properties according to the rate equations which describe the physical processes that control the degradation events, and sums the effects by calculating remaining global strength (to determine damage tolerance).

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of the present paper is to identify and discuss the manner in which the damage tolerance and durability of material systems such as continuous fiber reinforced composite materials is related to the synthesis, processing, and manufacturing of those systems. In colloquial terms, we will discuss how material systems "come apart" under long term use in terms of how they are "put together." We will attempt to show that damage tolerance and durability of material systems, unlike effective elastic properties, cannot be represented by models that are based on the linear superposition of the contribution of the constituents. Rather, damage and durability are actually "processes," in which interactions, events, sequences, and nonconservative material behavior are central to the physics and mechanics of the performance. Because of this fact, synthesis, processing, and manufacturing play an especially important role in the determination of the durability and damage tolerance of material systems.

FACTORS BELIEVED TO AFFECT DURABILITY

Stress Redistributions

According to the correspondence principle, engineering structures composed of a single linear viscoelastic material are not subject to stress redistributions due to viscoelastic behavior. For multiphase material systems, however, stress redistributions will occur, and can represent

significant shifts in stresses.[1] Such shifts may be beneficial when the load is transferred from a weaker, time dependent phase, such as the polymeric resin to the stronger fibers in FRP material systems. In some instances, however, such redistribution may actually worsen the situation for fibers which are already highly loaded, and which may act at the critical element in the overall failure process.

For nonlinear viscoelastic materials, stress redistribution will be more significant, and even single material systems are subject to stress redistributions. Since most real materials are expected to exhibit at least some nonlinearity, especially at higher stress/strain levels, nonlinear viscoelastic effects may be quite significant.[2] For more lightly loaded structures, the effects of nonlinear viscoelastic behavior are expected to be less, although perhaps not absent. Highly loaded regions around macro and micro-scopic stress concentrations may lead to nonlinear behavior which tends to accelerate damage and possibly degradation.

Damage mechanisms also result in stress redistributions which may be beneficial or deleterious. When compared with short term failures, static and dynamic fatigue both show considerably more damage. Damage states have been observed to develop over time even under (constant load) creep conditions.[3] In static fatigue, this damage may relieve highly stressed regions, and actually result in remaining strengths which are considerably higher than the static strength. (Remaining strengths as much as 30% higher than static strengths have been observed for several T300/934 laminates.)[4] As in dynamic fatigue, these damage mechanisms may increase over time to an extent that remaining strength drops and delayed creep-ruptures occur. An understanding of the manner in which damage accumulates with time in static fatigue is needed in order to better predict durability.

Constitutive Changes

Associated with stress redistribution is the concept of constitutive changes which occur. A number of investigators have shown that physical aging of composites can significantly alter the viscoelastic behavior.[5,6] In effect, large aging times can greatly retard the viscoelastic molecular motion, resulting in time response which is similar to that at temperatures much lower than the actual service temperatures. This has the effect of retarding both beneficial and detrimental stress redistributions. Other constitutive changes are possible, and may be effected by moisture, solvents, chemical reactions (additional cross-linking, post-curing, chain scissioning, etc.) A recent finding also suggests that the creep of certain composites may be significantly more affected by cyclic rather than continuously high moisture levels.[7,8,9]

Strength/Toughness Changes

The mechanisms mentioned above which affect constitutive behavior generally affect strength and toughness as well. Physical aging, for example, retards creep by making the material seem more glassy. This is generally believed to reduce the toughness of the material. Moisture sorption may actually increase strength and toughness in some (but not all) situations. Unreactive solvents may have mixed effects, as with moisture, although solvents which are sorbed to any significant extent will generally lead to reduced strengths (anti-plasticization). Recent work is suggesting that the combination of stress and solvent may be especially disastrous from some high performance resins, such as commercial formulations of LaRC-TPI. This environmental stress cracking may play havoc with structures with significant residual stresses which are subjected to typical aircraft cleaning fluids.

Figure 1 Creep rupture results for $[\pm 45, 90_2]_s$ laminates.

- Rapid strength degradation seen for an initial lot of AS4/J2 laminates at three temperatures.
- Slower (and similar) strength degradation at 120° for J2 composites with three fiber treatments.

Fiber/Matrix Effects

Recent work has produced mixed results concerning the effects of the interphase region on creep-rupture strength. Seemingly subtle changes in the fiber and matrix between two different batches of AS-4/J2 composites showed substantial differences in rates of strength degradation

in creep rupture as seen in Fig. 1. On the other hand, by carefully controlling the interphase with AU-4, AS-4, and AS-4CGP fiber treatments, the overall strength degradation rates were found to be almost identical.[10] This startling observation indicates that the role of the fiber/matrix interphase in determining creep rupture is not clear. Undoubtedly, some effects are present, but additional work is needed to sort out what aspects are critical for creep rupture behavior.

DAMAGE TOLERANCE OF MATERIAL SYSTEMS

Damage tolerance has a well established and accepted meaning in "design circles," and is the basis of several certification schemes for such things as commercial aircraft. The fundamental concept is illustrated by Fig. 2.

Figure 2 Schematic diagram of the damage tolerance concept.

Damage tolerance is defined by remaining strength. The concept assumes that the component in question is subjected to a long-term history of "loading" (which may be mechanical, chemical, and thermal environments), and that the properties of the component degrade or evolve during that service experience. The property of interest for damage tolerance is remaining strength.

The essence of the present paper is that strength (and durability) of a material system is not a "pure" material property; rather, it is defined by a process - a degradation and failure process that is closely related to the manner in which the material system was synthesized, processed, and manufactured. In the "classical" literature, the "rule of mixtures," superposition of elastic solutions, and "dilute solutions" are "accepted" as general discussions of composites, a fundamental error if strength is to be considered.[11,12] Let us consider the idea of "strength of a material system," and then discuss how it is related to the creation of the system itself.

It is difficult to discuss this topic in such a brief forum, and to address the myriad of details that are involved in the tensile, compression, and shear strengths of a composite material system. We will, instead, list "typical" events and processes which combine in various combinations for specific cases, and make the associations with synthesis, processing, and manufacturing which are the object of our paper.

1. Initial fracture of the constituents -

It is clear that **synthesis** controls the properties of the constituents. The stress level or strain level which causes a fiber or matrix material to break is proportional to the properties of the constituents themselves, which are controlled, in turn, by the synthesis of the constituents. Hence, initial damage initiation in the constituents is controlled by synthesis. We should note that local stress concentrations caused by processing and manufacturing may accelerate the initiation process by increasing the local stress in a constituent, and we should also note that the constituent material in a composite may not have the same properties as the "laboratory sample" of the constituent, since the formation history may not be the same. Beyond these caveats, this statement stands; **synthesis controls the properties of the constituents.**

2. Secondary damage initiation and growth -

Initial fracture of the constituents in a composite system rarely (if ever) causes failure of the composite (if it does, the composite is not properly designed). Secondary processes usually occur. When fibers break under tensile load in a polymer composite, for example, local plastic deformation of the matrix near the fiber fracture, slipping of the fiber-matrix interface, or local matrix crack formation and growth may be driven by the first event. In ceramic composites, the sequence might be matrix cracking, fiber-matrix interface slipping, fiber fragmentation, fiber pull-out, and fracture. For the secondary processes, synthesis has an influence on subsequent damage such as matrix cracking, but the processing of the fiber/matrix system will greatly influence the secondary damage process by, for example, altering the interface or interphase region between the fiber and matrix. From the standpoint of damage tolerance and durability, altering the interphase region between the fiber and matrix by processing may be a dominant feature. In ceramic composites, even the initial quasi-static strength can be altered by factors of 2 or 3 by introducing an interface or interphase region that allows local slipping between the fiber and matrix, so that matrix cracks do not prematurely cause fiber fracture. In polymer based systems, introducing a special interphase region can increase the static transverse strain to failure by 400 % and alter the notched fatigue life by a factor of more than 10![13,14] In fact, it would appear that altering the interfaces and interphases that connect the constituents, and, therefore, control the "system" effect or "composite effect" as we have discussed above, is one of the most important links between damage tolerance, and the design and processing of a material system.

Growth of damage such as delamination and (in some composite systems) self similar crack growth are also controlled by both constituent properties (synthesis) and the manner in which energy is distributed by the arrangement and geometry of constituents (processing).[15] The "fracture toughness" of a composite is often difficult to define, and may not be directly related to engineering behavior, per se. However, resistance to delamination can be an important feature from the standpoint of minimizing damage, although delamination is rarely a failure mode, as such. Ply delamination is greatly influenced by "manufacturing," i.e., by the orientation and stacking sequence of plies in a laminate.[16]

3. Damage interaction and failure initiation -

Damage tolerance involves the process of degradation over long periods of exposure to loading levels that do not cause immediate failure. Hence, eventual failure occurs when the properties of the material are reduced by damage to the level of applied load. In the (rare) instances when fracture is induced by the unstable growth of a single crack, failure is induced by an increase in the local field stress intensity at the tip of the growing crack. However, in most cases, the accumulation of damage and the interaction of the damage events combine to initiate the final failure event. This accumulation and interaction process depends on the properties, geometry,

and arrangement of the constituents (synthesis and processing) as discussed above, but it also depends on the statistical distribution of the properties of the constituents.[17] A simple way of illustrating this fact (in our limited space) is to consider the strength of a bundle of fibers (ignoring the effect of the matrix, for the purposes of our discussion). If the statistical distribution of fiber strengths is large, for example, then some fibers will begin to break at a very low load, compared to the average strength of the fibers. The load released by the fracture of those fibers must be carried by the remaining fibers, i.e., the early fractures mean that the remaining unbroken fibers have a larger load to carry for a given global applied load. As the applied load is increased, the bundle will fail at a lower applied load than would be the case if all fiber had exactly the same strength (the average fiber strength) with no statistical spread. Also, the local distribution of stress around a fiber break, for example, is determined by the stiffness, geometry, and arrangement of the constituents, and the chance that the next nearest fiber (and eventually the composite) will break is determined by the **interaction** between that nonuniform stress state and the distribution of fiber strengths (as a function of position) in that neighboring region. Changing either the local stress distribution or the strength distribution will change the global composite strength, a most surprising result.

MODELING OF DAMAGE TOLERANCE

A performance simulation code, called "MRLife," has been constructed and assembled to provide a mechanism for combining the knowledge and information discussed above. The conceptual concept associated with the code is suggested by Fig. 3. We have discussed this approach in several previous papers.[18,19,20] Calculation of the remaining strength (for each distinct failure mode) is done by the equation at the bottom of Fig. 3. Degradation of the constituents and interfaces or interphases is incorporated into a "failure criteria," *Fa*, which compare the local state of stress to the local state of material to determine remaining strength. The form of the failure criterion is determined by the nature of the specific failure mode in question, and that failure mode also specifies the boundary value problem that is ultimately solved to estimate the local state of stress (using a representative volume approach). This approach has shown good agreement with experimental observations.[18,19,20]

Figure 3 Associations between synthesis, processing, manufacturing, and performance simulation.

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